

CORROSION INHIBITION OF ALUMINUM ALLOYS WITH SODIUM BENZOATE IN ACIDIC ENVIRONMENTS: A CURRENT LITERATURE REVIEW FOR RESEARCH GAPS

T.N. Guma and Olagunju R. Atinuke

Department of Mechanical Engineering, Faculty of Engineering and Technology, Nigerian Defence Academy,
Kaduna, Nigeria

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Abstract: This paper presents a current literature review of the general uses, production, availability level, and cost of sodium benzoate, showcasing it as an effective and eco-friendly corrosion inhibitor of aluminum alloys in acidic environments. The study aims to reveal any research gaps or limitations in its usage as a corrosion inhibitor. The study shows that aluminum alloys are some of the most important and best structural metals used in modern engineering and construction, and acidic environments are among the most common corrosion-aggressive types of environments to which they are frequently exposed. Aluminum alloys are often used as lightweight alternatives to steel for certain components or systems that need to be strong, light, and resistant to corrosion. However, acidic environments are capable of degrading the thin protective oxide coating that is often instantly formed on the surface of the alloys on exposure to oxygen, accelerating pitting corrosion, general surface attack, and other corrosion forms of the alloys as the environmental acidity level increases. Sodium benzoate is an organic salt with significant industrial applications in acidic environments. It is manufactured globally on a large scale and is available at cost-effective rates and sustainably in most countries, including Nigeria. According to reports, it works best to lower the corrosion rates of aluminum alloys in near-neutral to alkaline environments with pH values between 6 and 12. Its corrosion inhibition efficiency increases with the concentration and immersion time of the alloys in the environment. However, its inhibition performance data on aluminum alloys in highly acidic solutions of less than 5.5 pH has not been reconciled from the literature, and there is an indication that the corrosion inhibition decreases as the pH decreases downwards from 4. Some claims of sodium benzoate converting to benzoic acid and to benzene, a carcinogen, require further research, including field studies, to confirm some initial findings about its safety and optimal corrosion inhibition using individual aluminum alloys and pH in highly acidic conditions for its better usage.

Key words: Aluminum alloys, corrosion, acidic environments, inhibition, sodium benzoate, current knowledge, review findings, research gaps, research progress

1.0 INTRODUCTION

Aluminum alloys are generally classified under the 1xxx, 2xxx, 3xxx, 4xxx, 5xxx, 6xxx, 7xxx, and 8xxx series, of which the 1xxx, 3xxx, 4xxx, and 5xxx series are non-heat-treatable alloys [1-3]. Non-heat-treatable alloys have higher aluminum content, lower strength, and higher resistance to general corrosion than other aluminum alloys

[1-3]. The 2xxx, 6xxx, and 7xxx series are heat-treatable to enhance their properties, including corrosion resistance [1-7]. Aluminum alloys have significant applications in various industries [1-4, 8-13]:

- i. Aerospace, where some aircraft components, wings, and fuselages, such as the 2000 and 7000 series, are used for high strength-to-weight performance.
- ii. Automotive and transportation, where they are used in engine blocks, pistons, body panels, and chassis to reduce weight, improve fuel efficiency, and enhance crash safety.
- iii. Construction and architecture, where they are used for window frames, doors, roofs, and facades due to their durability, corrosion resistance, and structural strength.
- iv. Marine, where some are used for ship hulls, railings, and decking due to their corrosion resistance to seawater.
- v. Electrical and electronic components used in high-voltage power lines and electronic components for heat management.
- vi. Consumer goods and packaging are used for beverage cans, foil, appliances, and cookware because they are non-toxic, lightweight, and durable.

When aluminum alloys come into contact with oxygen, they instantly form a thin aluminum oxide (Al_2O_3) coating on their surfaces. The oxide coating is extremely hard, difficult to penetrate, and self-restoring, protecting them from environmental hazards. The protective oxide layer makes them much more resistant to corrosion than many other metals [8-13]. The optimal pH value for the stable oxide layer ranges between 4 and 9, whereas acidic and alkaline environments outside this range will degrade the oxide layer and cause pitting in the exposed surface of the alloys. Acidic environments of pH 4 are among the most aggressive environments to which aluminum and its alloys are frequently exposed for long periods. On exposure to such environments, the protective oxide layer on the alloy surfaces is chemically dissolved, exposing the underlying metal to rapid corrosion [8-14]. The key areas of application of aluminum alloys in acidic environments in various industries and the risk of dangerous corrosion are as follows [1-7, 15-18]:

- i. Chemical handling through industrial processing such as etching to achieve a matte, uniform, or smooth surface finish; bright dipping to polish and brighten surfaces; acidic cleaning/brightening of vehicles to remove road grime, stains, and light oxidation from aluminum wheels or other surfaces; and pickling and descaling processes often involving hydrochloric, sulfuric, nitric, and phosphoric acids separately or their various combination levels.
- ii. Environmental exposure, accident-related operational acid spillage, cleaning, storage, and transportation equipment that handle acidic solutions
- iii. Marine, automobile, aircraft, and overhead electrical transmission components, such as frames, beams, wires, and panels, which may face acidic conditions, including acid fog or rain, that break down the protective oxide layer.
- iv. Acidic processing of aluminum components involving removal of thick, natural oxide layers prior to some welding such as spot welding; surface preparation of components prior to electroplating by removing contaminants before applying a zincate layer; surface treatment for adhesive bonding to create a porous oxide structure that enhances adhesive strength; and chemical milling or etching to remove material from specific areas of aerospace or automotive parts.
- v. Cooking food and beverage packaging, where they can be exposed to acidic components in food products.
- vi. The use of aluminum cookware such as pots, pans, and baking sheets to prepare acidic dishes such as tomato sauce, citrus-based sauces, and vinegars creates direct contact; wrapping, covering, or baking food in aluminum foil allows acids to interact more with the metal, making it particularly risky when using foil to cover acidic, salty, or spiced foods, which can speed up corrosion, and leftovers, particularly acidic foods like fruits,

tomatoes, or sauerkraut, in aluminum containers or wrapped in foil for extended periods exacerbate corrosion. These are worsened at higher temperatures, unprotected aluminum and/or scratched and pitted aluminum cookware or foil, as well as the synergistic penetrating effects of higher acidity and salt content of the food on the protective film, and cause pitting corrosion of the bare metal.

The industry uses several mitigation strategies to prevent direct environmental contact and leaching of aluminum alloys, such as anodization, which is used to thicken the natural oxide layer on aluminum, making the surface non-reactive and safe for acidic foods; the use of polymer coatings on most modern beverage cans and food trays made of aluminum metal to isolate the food from the metal; cladding of some cookware in non-reactive materials like stainless steel to combine aluminum's heat distribution with safer contact; and use of corrosion inhibitors [3-6, 15-18]. The use of corrosion inhibitors is a common, versatile, and cost-effective method in aqueous environments. It can be used alone or in various combinations with the other protective methods to supplement them for greater corrosion protection of the alloys. Suitable corrosion inhibitors can significantly reduce aluminum corrosion to minimal levels during acidic cleaning, pickling, etching, and other industrial processes. They are suitable for the preparation of aluminum alloys in various acidic environments, including hydrochloric, sulfuric, and phosphoric acids [15-18]. They reduce aluminum metal loss during industrial processes, such as pickling, and prevent hydrogen embrittlement [15-18]. Organic corrosion inhibitors are often added to acid baths made of aluminum alloys and other processing equipment to prevent catastrophic equipment degradation; however, most of them present toxicity problems and/or environmental unfriendliness [3-7, 15-18]. They offer high inhibition efficiency, often exceeding 95%, of aluminum alloys by forming a protective adsorbed film on the surface. Some inhibitors remain effective even under harsh, thermally elevated conditions [15-18]. Organic compounds containing nitrogen, oxygen, or sulfur, such as amines, thiourea, and triazole, which inhibit corrosion by forming protective layers on metal surfaces, are the most common corrosion inhibitors for aluminum alloys in acidic environments [15-18]. Other corrosion inhibitors for aluminum alloys include heterocyclic compounds, inorganic salts (silicates), plant extracts, and honey [3-7, 15-18]. Natural products or green inhibitors offer a sustainable way to prevent corrosion and provide an environmentally friendly, cost-effective alternative to toxic organic inhibitors and traditional inorganic inhibitors, such as chromates and dichromates, which are effective but highly toxic and pose severe environmental risks [15-18].

Currently, there is much research on developing corrosion inhibitors for aluminum alloys in acidic environments. The research need is driven by the need for the best way of protecting this widely used metal from rapid dissolution in aggressive industrial processes while simultaneously addressing the environmental toxicity of traditional inhibitors and the increased sensitivity of new, high-strength alloys through the development of "green," eco-friendly alternatives, such as plant extracts or biodegradable organic compounds, that are safe yet efficient. However, research on the development of corrosion inhibitors for aluminum alloys in acidic environments must establish the inhibitors' individual effectiveness, stability, mechanism of action, sustained availability, cost, and environmental friendliness before adopting them [3-7, 15-18].

Sodium benzoate is a popular non-toxic organic salt that has wide industrial applications in acidic environments, including effective corrosion inhibition of aluminum alloys in acidic environments such as sulfuric or hydrochloric acids [19, 20]. It is considered a mixed-type inhibitor that reduces both anodic and cathodic reactions and acts as an adsorption-type inhibitor, forming a thin, protective film on the aluminum surface to stop metallic dissolution [15-19]. This paper presents a review report on the various uses, production, availability, and cost of sodium benzoate as supported by research on its applications in acidic environments, including corrosion inhibition of aluminum alloys, to showcase its environmental friendliness and other desirable safety properties as a corrosion inhibitor, and to provide any research gaps on its corrosion inhibition performance for research progress on the subject.

2.0 METHODOLOGY

The current literature information on sodium benzoate covering its physical and chemical characteristics, general uses, possible health problems in usage, production, availability, cost-effectiveness, research for general applications showcasing its environmental friendliness and service properties as a strong corrosion inhibitor, and research on its corrosion-inhibiting capability of aluminum alloys in acidic environments was sourced from relevant reputable journals, theses, books, books of conference proceedings, business websites on the INTERNET, and institutional libraries. The obtained information was integrated and fine-tuned, and areas where its use for corrosion inhibition of aluminum alloys in acidic environments has not been addressed were revealed for further research to consolidate its inhibition information for better application purposes.

3.0 REVIEW REPORT

3.1 Sodium benzoate as a Material

3.1.1 Physical and chemical characteristics of the samples

Sodium benzoate is a widely used chemical preservative and food additive that appears as a white crystalline powder. It is the sodium salt of benzoic acid. It is highly soluble in water and is extensively employed to inhibit the growth of mold, yeast, and bacteria in acidic environments (typically pH 4.5). It is designated with the E number E211. It is a colorless, odorless organic sodium salt with a chemical formula of $C_7H_5NaO_2$, a molar mass of 144.105 g/mol, a density of 1.497 g/cm³, and a melting point of 410°C. It is highly soluble in water, as indicated by solubilities of 62.65 g/100 mL, 62.84 g/100 mL, 62.87 g/100 mL, and 74.2 g/100 mL at 0, 15, 30, and 100°C, respectively. Fig. 1 shows the chemical structure of the as-manufactured pure form of sodium benzoate [19-21].

Fig 1: Chemical structure of sodium benzoate and its as-manufactured pure form [20].

3.1.2 General uses

Sodium benzoate is the most commonly and widely used [22-24]:

i. Preservatives used in the food industry to protect foods and beverages. It is used to prevent spoilage from harmful bacteria, yeast, and mold. It also helps maintain freshness in food by slowing or preventing color, flavor, pH, and texture changes. Some foods that commonly contain sodium benzoate for preservation are salad dressings, pickles, condiments, fruit juices, wines, and snack foods. It is generally recognized as safe (GRAS), meaning that experts consider it safe when used as intended. It is approved internationally as a food additive and is assigned the identifying number 211. For example, it is listed as E211 in European food products. It inhibits the growth of potentially harmful bacteria, mold, and other microbes in food, thereby deterring spoilage. It is particularly effective against acidic foods. Because of these qualities, foods with an acidic pH, such as soda, bottled lemon juice, jelly, and salad dressing, are commonly used. Soy sauce, fruit purees and pulps, jams, pickles, pickled herring and mackerel, margarine, olives, beer, fruit yogurts, canned vegetables, and salads are preserved with sodium benzoate. Sodium benzoate is most frequently added to sauces, tomato paste, fruit preserves, mayonnaise, margarine, carbonated beverages, and other condiments.

- ii. Preservative in soft drinks to increase the acidity of flavor and extend shelf life. For example, sodium benzoate, potassium benzoate, and potassium sorbate are the three common preservatives in Coca-Cola that protect the taste and fight microbes. It is among the main ingredients of Fanta, Sprite, and Pepsi carbonated soft drinks for preserving their freshness. It is also used as the main preservative in smaller amounts in PepsiCo's popular soda, Diet Pepsi.
- iii. Preservatives in some over-the-counter and prescription medications, particularly in liquid medicines such as cough syrup, for neurodivergent-disorder medications. It is considered a pain reliever for chronic pain but has yet to show effectiveness toward acute pain. One possible explanation for its analgesic effects is that it is a D-AAO inhibitor. The potential significance of these inhibitors in the management of neuropathic pain and chronic pain, including pain related to bone cancer, has been demonstrated. It is a lubricant used in pill manufacturing that makes tablets transparent and smooth, thereby helping them to break down rapidly after swallowing. Lastly, larger amounts of sodium benzoate can be prescribed to treat elevated blood levels of ammonia as a byproduct of protein breakdown and blood levels that may become dangerously high in certain medical conditions.
- iv. Medicinal for the treatment of inflammation and bronchial dilation, as well as bacterial stomatitis, due to its expectorant and disinfectant effects. It prevents corrosion in surgical instrument storage fluids and is sometimes used as an ingredient in disinfectants. According to Medical Research and Development, it is used to treat various mental disorders, such as panic attacks, although this finding is not conclusive.
- v. Anti-corrosive and preservative properties of skin care products such as moisturizers, serums, and sunscreens. Shampoos and soaps can also contain sodium benzoate.
- vi. Preservative for inhibiting the growth of microbes in personal care products, such as toothpaste, because of its antimicrobial effect, safety, and low price.
- vii. Anticorrosive additive to paints and coatings. It can also be used as an ingredient in adhesives, lubricants, antifreeze, sealants, and other car care products.
- viii. Preservative in cosmetics and personal care items, such as hair products, baby wipes, toothpaste, and mouthwash.
- ix. Corrosion inhibitor or deterrent, such as in car engine coolants.
- x. Stabilizer in photo processing and to improve the strength of some plastics.
- xi. Ingredient in making perfumes, baby products, and other body refreshments

3.1.3 Possible health problems associated with usage

Although sodium benzoate is generally very environmentally friendly and safe in human bodies at low levels, such as those found in beverages. The FDA has stated that the low levels of benzene found in beverages do not pose a health risk. The International Program on Chemical Safety has found no adverse effect of sodium benzoate in humans at doses of 647-825 mg/kg of body weight. The FDA considers the maximum allowable level for sodium benzoate in drinking water to be 5 parts per billion, whereas the WHO sets the allowable level of sodium benzoate in consumable products at 0-5 milligrams per kilogram of human body weight per day. The Food and Drug Administration (FDA) also allows up to a 0.1% concentration of sodium benzoate by weight in foods and beverages. However, preliminary studies have raised safety questions about sodium benzoate that need more research for confirmation due to its ability to convert to benzene, a known carcinogen. Other risks of sodium benzoate suggested by preliminary studies include cancer-promoting inflammatory pathways in the body in direct proportion to its amount consumed, obesity, oxidative stress, and attention deficit hyperactivity disorder in some children with higher intake of sodium benzoate in beverages. The sodium benzoate additive in foods and beverages has also been linked to appetite suppression, free radicals that can damage body cells and increase the risk of chronic disease, and allergic reactions such as itching and swelling in some people after consuming foods or using personal care products that contain sodium benzoate [25].

3.1.4 Production, availability, and cost

Sodium benzoate is a widely available, low-cost preservative that is produced by neutralizing benzoic acid with sodium hydroxide. It is manufactured on a large scale, with over 150,000 metric tons produced annually, and is commonly found in acidic foods, pharmaceuticals, and cosmetics. It is produced by the neutralization process, principally by reacting benzoic acid with sodium hydroxide in an aqueous solution to form sodium benzoate, oxidizing toluene to form benzoic acid, which is then neutralized with sodium hydroxide, reacting benzoyl chloride with sodium hydroxide, and the manufacturing processes that typically include a neutralizing reaction, decolorization with activated carbon, filtration, and drying to create granules or powder. It is highly available and easily obtainable from chemical suppliers, online retailers, and industrial distributors worldwide, with a significant output from China, the United States, and Germany, with Asia-Pacific holding the largest market share in 2025. Currency fluctuations highly influence the price of sodium benzoate in Nigeria and most other developing countries. As of late 2025 and early 2026, one kilogram of sodium benzoate roughly ranged from ₦2,500 to ₦4,860 in price, while one ton (1,000 kg) generally cost over two million Naira [26, 27].

3.1.5 Some recent research on its applications showcasing its safe properties and corrosion inhibition capability on aluminum alloys in acidic environment

Walczak-Nowicka and Herbet [28] contended that due to the large number of reports regarding the harmfulness of food additives, more and more consumers are currently following the so-called “clean label” trend, i.e., prefer and choose the least-processed food products. A compound known as a high-safety preservative is sodium benzoate. While some studies have revealed that it can be used to treat conditions such as depression, pain, schizophrenia, autism spectrum disorders, and neurodegenerative diseases, others have reported that it is harmful. For example, it causes mutagenic effects, generates oxidative stress, disrupts hormones, and reduces fertility. Due to such disparate results, this study aimed to comprehensively discuss the safety profile of sodium benzoate and its potential use in neurodegenerative diseases, especially in autism spectrum disorder, schizophrenia, major depressive disorder, and pain relief.

Mohammed and Issa [29] presented a short overview that summarizes the dual role of sodium benzoate (SB) as a useful preservative and a possible threat to human and environmental health. This review provides a concise summary of the uses, adverse effects, and environmental impact of SB. Because of its ability to inhibit microbial growth, SB is widely used as a preservative in pharmaceuticals and food products, thus extending the shelf life of various formulations, including syrups and ointments. Although generally considered safe, SB can cause allergic reactions and may contribute to conditions such as ADHD, particularly in children. It can also disrupt the gut microbiota balance. This paper highlights the concerns regarding the environmental persistence of SB. Although it is biodegradable, its degradation rate can vary depending on the conditions and concentrations. Improper wastewater treatment can lead to its accumulation in aquatic ecosystems, posing risks to both the environment and human health. The review emphasizes the need for awareness regarding the long-term effects of sodium benzoate in ecosystems, which its impact can be mitigated by environmentally friendly technologies. Pongsetkul and Benjakul [30] assessed the quality changes and shelf life of dried chili fish paste treated with 0.1% sodium benzoate (SB) and stored in various packaging containers, including polypropylene (PP+SB), polyethylene-terephthalate (PET+SB), and LLDPE-aluminum Ziplock bag (ZL+SB), during a 20-week storage period at room temperature (25°C–28°C) compared with samples without preservatives (PP, PET, and ZL). Samples treated with 0.1% SB exhibited a slower rate of quality changes throughout storage, including pH, browning index, oxidation products, and microorganisms. These samples can be stored at room temperature for at least 20 weeks without spoilage. Moreover, their sensorial scores, assessed by 50 untrained panelists who were familiar with this product, were more than 7.0 in all aspects, for example, color, flavor, and texture. In contrast, samples without preservatives, which revealed a higher rate of changes in all quality characteristics, underwent

spoilage during a 20-week storage period at different times depending on the packaging container. The shelf life of PP, PET, and ZL was 6, 10, and 10 weeks, respectively, as indicated by the excess of total microorganisms ($>1.00 \times 10^4$ CFU/g sample). Overall, the results indicated that 0.1% sodium benzoate can effectively extend the shelf life of dried chili fish paste for at least 5 months with prime quality.

Kaur and Jawandha [31] examined the effect of postharvest applications of sodium benzoate on the physicochemical properties and enzymatic activities of pear fruit cv. Patharnakh during cold storage. Uniform and healthy pear cv. fruits Patharnakh samples were treated with 0.0, 1.0, 2.0, and 3.0% sodium benzoate and stored at low temperatures (0°C – 1°C and 90%–95% relative humidity) for 70 days. The physicochemical parameters and enzymatic activities were evaluated at 0, 20, 40, 60, and 70 days of storage. It was found that sodium benzoate treatments effectively retained higher fruit firmness, sensory quality, and total phenolic content and suppressed the degradation of total soluble solids, ascorbic acid content, and titratable acidity. Sodium benzoate-treated fruits also exhibited higher efficacy in maintaining less enzymatic activity of cellulase, pectin methyl esterase, and polyphenol oxidase. It was inferred that the postharvest treatment with sodium benzoate is an effective means of improving the quality and postharvest life of 'Patharnakh' pear fruit.

Shahmohammadi et al. [32] submitted that food spoilage has been a common problem throughout history, and the activity of microorganisms or enzymatic reactions during food storage cause much of the spoilage. Thus, the use of chemical substances could prevent or delay food spoilage, and this has led to the great success of these compounds for treating human diseases. Sodium benzoate is a synthetic additive widely used in the food industry. In their review, the authors summarized the history and role of sodium benzoate in the food industry, its limited value in different foods, other uses, pharmacokinetics, and its toxicity in animal studies. A literature search was conducted using MEDLINE, Scopus, Science Direct, and Scientific Information Databases. The results revealed that sodium benzoate is used in different industries as well as the food industry, and it has similar adverse effects to other food additives. The study concluded that studies on natural ingredients in foods are necessary to find compounds with similar effects as benzoate with fewer adverse effects.

Linke et al. [33] contended that food additives are widely used by the food industry to increase the product shelf life and/or attribute as well as enhance certain characteristics of particular foods, which are often lost during processing. With the advent of modern life, the food industry has employed more and more additives. Despite their wide use, they are substances that may cause adverse reactions like any other drug. This study aimed to contextualize the scientific evidence on the risks entailed by the consumption of food additives, with special regard to sodium benzoate, through a literature review. This additive is a sodium salt that is commonly used as a chemical preservative in foods and is mainly found in industrialized drinks/beverages. Sodium benzoate is considered safe by major regulatory agencies, but its effects on human health remain controversial.

Azuma et al. [34] submitted that the use of sodium benzoate in non-alcoholic carbonated (soft) drinks is a serious concern because of its mechanistic ability to convert to benzene, a classified carcinogen. This concern drove this study to determine consumer exposures to sodium benzoate and possible health risks from the intake of such soft drinks. A survey was conducted during which Google Forms was used to collect drink consumption data from 113 consumers, including males and females. During the same period, 38 varieties of non-alcoholic carbonated (soft) drinks were collected from two major Ghanaian markets. Subsequently, these drink samples were subjected to extraction protocols, and the levels of sodium benzoate were quantified using high-performance liquid chromatography. Information from the Google Forms, with the quantification of sodium benzoate, formed the basis of the determination of sodium benzoate exposure according to the USEPA protocols. Using the Palisade @Risk software, elements of exposure to sodium benzoate (mg/mL ingested, volume in mL of non-alcoholic carbonated (soft) drink consumed, and body weight in kg of consumers) were integrated and iterated (at 105) to estimate the simulated chronic exposures. Simulated risks (hazard quotient, HQ; margin of exposure, MOE; and

LTCR) were determined using thresholds obtained from regulatory bodies. High levels of sodium benzoate, above the acceptable limit of 150 mg/L based on USEPA recommendations, were detected in 6 (16%) of the 38 non-alcoholic carbonated (soft) drinks sampled. The results of the study showed that the sodium benzoate concentrations ranged from a minimum of 51.0 mg/L to a maximum of 277.0 mg/L. It was clear that the consumption patterns of males created relatively high exposures, leading to unsurprisingly higher risks compared to female consumers. The high-risk indices determined in this study, relative to regulatory thresholds ($HQ > 1$, $MOE < 104$, and $LTCR > 10^{-6}$), are all serious indicators of grave public health concerns. These observations emphasize the potential of benzenes in our food chains and call for a more forceful monitoring of product quality and safety to ensure adherence to standards.

Nik et al. [35] asserted that corrosion is a fundamental process that plays an important role in economics and safety. Corrosion cannot be avoided, but its severity can be prevented. Inhibitors have always been considered the first line of defense against corrosion. Several corrosion inhibitors are currently available. Their study aimed to evaluate the effectiveness of sodium benzoate as an inhibitor to slow down or prevent corrosion. Their study involved the use of gravimetric measurements, potentiodynamic polarization, and electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) to evaluate the inhibitive action of sodium benzoate on the corrosion behavior of AA6063 aluminum alloy in seawater. The electrochemical measurements showed that the presence of sodium benzoate as an inhibitor significantly decreased the weight loss, corrosion current densities (i_{corr}), corrosion rates, and double-layer capacitance (C_{dl}), while increasing the polarization resistance (R_p).

Bakar [36] used two different experimental methods to confirm the ability of sodium benzoate to inhibit the corrosion of aluminum in diluted sulfuric acid and diluted hydrochloric acid. The inhibition efficiency and corrosion rate of sodium benzoate were determined using the polarization method and weight loss measurement. The results showed that sodium benzoate behaved as a cathodic corrosion inhibitor and mixed corrosion inhibitor in diluted sulfuric acid and diluted hydrochloric acid, respectively. The results from both the polarization method and weight loss measurement showed that the highest inhibition efficiency was achieved at a sodium benzoate concentration of 800 ppm.

Rafi-ud-din et al. [37] disclosed that sodium benzoate (SB) was used for the first time to inhibit the corrosion of Al6061-B4C composites in H_3BO_3 and NaCl solutions. Al6061100-x-x wt% B4C ($x = 0, 5, \text{ and } 10$) composites were manufactured using a powder metallurgy method. The corrosion inhibition efficiency of SB was investigated as a function of the volume fractions of B4C particles using potentiodynamic polarization and electrochemical impedance techniques. Without the use of an inhibitor, an increase of the B4C particles in the composite decreased the corrosion resistance of Al6061-B4C composites. SB is an efficient corrosion inhibitor for Al6061-B4C composites in both investigated solutions. The corrosion inhibition efficiency of SB increased with the increase in the B4C content. Since SB is an adsorption-type inhibitor, an extremely thin layer of molecules is envisaged to adsorb onto the surface and suppress oxidation and reduction. The inhibitor effect of SB was more pronounced in an H_3BO_3 environment than in a NaCl solution. Furthermore, the mechanism of corrosion inhibition by SB was illustrated using optical and scanning electron microscopy of corroded samples. The adsorption of benzoate ions on the Al surface and its bonding with Al^{3+} ions formed a hydrophobic layer on top of the exposed Al surface, which enhanced the protection against dissolved boride ions.

Wormwell et al [38] carried out 60 tests in working vehicles. To establish the benzoate/nitrite corrosion inhibitor's efficiency in service conditions. The testing technique and method of assessing the results were described. Of special importance is the need to conduct parallel tests in several vehicles because of the varying corrosion rates in different vehicles carrying the same coolant. The tests have shown that the addition of 1.5% sodium benzoate with 0.1% sodium nitrite to 20% or 33 1/3% solutions of ethylene glycol will effectively prevent the cast iron corrosion of the cylinder block or head in the usual engine system. The corrosion of the radiator unit will also be

prevented. The study concluded that the benzoate/nitrite inhibitor does not always prevent the corrosion of aluminum alloys.

Pruthviraj [39] noted that various types of destructive attacks can occur to marine structures, ships, and other equipment used in seawater service. The cost of marine corrosion has increased annually, and it is estimated at 4% of the Gross National Product. Aluminum alloys are important materials that are commonly used in marine applications. In this study, aluminum 2024 was subjected to seawater. Sodium benzoate was used as a corrosion inhibitor for aluminum alloys in aggressive marine environments. To study the corrosion behavior of aluminum alloy AA2024 in seawater, the electrochemical behavior of aluminum alloy was investigated using different inhibitor concentrations, potentiodynamic polarization, and electrochemical spectroscopy (EIS). The morphology study was carried out to observe the development of the thin film on the specimen, and this study was conducted using SEM. The EIS data showed that the corrosion mechanism depends on the inhibitor concentration.

Wong et al. [40] stated that sodium benzoate is ideally suited for application in engine coolant as both an antimicrobial agent and corrosion inhibitor. Their study evaluated the antimicrobial and anticorrosion properties of sodium benzoate in an ethylene glycol-based organic engine coolant. Antimicrobial assays tested sodium benzoate against *Bacillus cereus*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, and *Trichoderma* species. The corrosion inhibitory effect was assessed using the ASTM D1384 corrosion test. It was found that 3% wt. sodium benzoate strongly inhibited microbial growth, whereas a minimum dosage of 1% wt. only mild antimicrobial performance. The presence of 50% ethylene glycol in the coolant outperformed sodium benzoate in terms of antimicrobial effectiveness. Sodium benzoate also exhibited selective corrosion protection; at a 1% wt. dosage, it offered superior protection for aluminum but promoted iron corrosion.

Following standard experimental (gravimetric measurements, potentiodynamic polarization measurements, electrochemical impedance measurements, spectroscopic measurements, and scanning electron microscopy technique) and theoretical (DFT) approaches, Parveen et al. [41] studied the inhibition effect of L-proline (LPr) and LPr mixed with sodium benzoate (LPr + NaBenz) for mild steel (MS) corrosion in 1 M HCl at 30, 40, 50, and 60°C. The LPr concentration was varied between 100 and 600 ppm, whereas that of NaBenz was fixed at 10 ppm. LPr lowered the corrosion rates of the MS considerably. The corrosion-mitigating efficacy of LPr is synergistically enhanced upon the addition of NaBenz at all concentrations. The evaluation of polarization parameters suggested that both LPr and LPr + NaBenz acted as mixed-type inhibitors with more control on the cathodic reaction, whereas the impedance parameters suggested the inhibition of metal corrosion by adsorption at the MS/solution interface. Surface microscopic examination of corroded and uncorroded MS coupons supported the protective effect of the adsorbed inhibitor layer at the MS surface. Spectroscopic studies exhibit the formation of a complex between inhibitor molecules and the metal. When LPr is combined with NaBenz, the corrosion inhibition rate is greatly improved. The corrosion-mitigating efficacy of LPr or LPr mixed with NaBenz obtained using different techniques is in good agreement with the theoretical quantum chemical descriptors.

According to Muzathik et al. [42], "corrosion is chemically induced damage to a material that results in deterioration of the material and its properties." Ships, marinas, pipelines, offshore structures, desalination plants, and heat exchangers are some examples of systems that have experienced marine corrosion. Aluminum alloy is commonly used in marine applications. The use of inhibitors is a practical method for corrosion protection. Sodium benzoate has found considerable application as a low-concentration corrosion inhibitor". This study aimed to analyze the corrosion behavior of aluminum AA 7618 alloy toward tropical seawater in the presence of sodium benzoate as a corrosion inhibitor for industrial applications. Immersion and electrochemical tests were conducted to measure corrosion. The immersion period of the aluminum alloy was 60 days. A seawater sample was collected from the South China Sea along Universiti Malaysia Terengganu. Their study reported the results of weight loss, inhibition efficiency, corrosion rate (mm/year), corrosion current density (i_{corr}), corrosion

potential (E_{corr}), polarization resistance (R_p), and capacitance (CPE). The addition of sodium benzoate acted as an inhibitor and minimized the corrosion of the aluminum alloy in seawater. The inhibition efficiency increases as the immersion time increases. Electrochemical studies showed a significant increase in the overall resistance after the addition of sodium benzoate. The inhibition efficiency increased from 50% to 97% during the immersion period and increased with the immersion time. The result obtained concluded that sodium benzoate is suitable as a corrosion inhibitor of AA 7618 alloy in seawater.

Uwiringiyimana et al. [43] summarized the effect of inhibitors on the corrosion of stainless steels and aluminum alloys in acidic and other media. They noted that aluminum alloys and stainless steels have various applications in construction, transport, domestic appliances, medical, and energy-related fields. However, the exposure of stainless steels and aluminum alloys to corroding environments can result in their degradation with adverse consequences. Inhibitors are often used to mitigate the corrosion degradation of these alloys in various media to enhance their durability. Corrosion inhibitors can be anodic, cathodic, mixed, or volatile. Their review showed that inhibition efficiency increases with an increase in inhibitor concentration irrespective of the alloy tested. However, the adsorption of inhibitors on the surface of alloys depends on the alloy type. The adsorption of inhibitors on the surfaces of stainless steels and aluminum alloys obeyed Langmuir, Temkin, Flory-Huggins, and Freundlich isotherms. This study is important for different industrial fields where stainless steels and aluminum alloys are used.

Rosliza et al. [44] asserted that the corrosion inhibition of aluminum and its alloys is of tremendous technological importance due to the increased industrial applications of these materials. This study reports the results of weight loss, polarization, and electrochemical impedance spectroscopic (EIS) measurements on the corrosion inhibition of AA6061 and AA6063 aluminum alloys in acidic solutions using sodium benzoate as an inhibitor. The results showed that the addition of sodium benzoate retards the dissolution rate and hence inhibits the corrosion of the aluminum alloy in acidic solutions. The inhibition efficiency increases with the immersion time in acetic acid; however, it exhibits a different behavior in sulfuric acid. Electrochemical studies showed a significant increase in overall resistance after the addition of sodium benzoate compared with the case without an inhibitor. The Langmuir adsorption isotherm fits well with the experimental data.

Rosliza et al. [45] contended that the corrosion inhibition of Al and its alloys is of tremendous technological importance due to the increased industrial applications of these materials. This study reports the results of weight loss, polarization, and electrochemical impedance spectroscopic (EIS) measurements on the corrosion inhibition of AA6061 and AA6063 aluminum alloys in acidic media using sodium benzoate as an inhibitor. The results showed that the addition of sodium benzoate retards the dissolution rate and hence inhibits the corrosion of the aluminum alloy in acidic media. The inhibition efficiency increases with the immersion time in acetic acid; however, it exhibits a different behavior in sulfuric acid. The Langmuir adsorption isotherm fits well with the experimental data. EIS studies showed a significant increase in overall resistance after the addition of sodium benzoate compared with the case without the inhibitor. The Langmuir adsorption isotherm fits well with the experimental data.

Deepa and Padmalatha [46] investigated the corrosion behavior of 6063 aluminum alloy in different phosphoric acid and sodium hydroxide medium concentrations at different temperatures. The study was conducted by electrochemical method, using Tafel polarization technique and electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) technique. The surface morphology was investigated using scanning electron microscopy (SEM) with energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDX). The results showed that the 6063-aluminum alloy undergoes more severe corrosion in the sodium hydroxide medium than in the phosphoric acid medium. The corrosion rate of the 6063-aluminum alloy increased with an increase in the concentration of acid and alkali. The corrosion rate increased with increasing temperature. The kinetic and thermodynamic parameters were calculated using the Arrhenius and

transition state theories. A suitable mechanism for the corrosion of 6063 aluminum alloy in a phosphoric acid and sodium hydroxide medium was proposed. The results obtained by Tafel polarization and EIS techniques agreed well with each other.

The goal of the current investigation by Singh et al. [47] was to examine the corrosion effect of aluminum 6061 alloys using an acidic immersion corrosion experiment. Experiments were conducted in accordance with the L_9 orthogonal array tables with two corrosion parameters: acidic solution and immersion duration with three levels. Taguchi's methodology optimizes the corrosion parameters to obtain a minimum corrosion rate on aluminum 6061 alloys. The results reveal that the chloride ions cause significant corrosion in the aluminum alloy samples dipped in a hydrochloric acidic solution. Significant possible corrosion occurred in the initial stage of the immersion of the samples in the acidic solution. This is due to the termination of a protective aluminum oxide layer over the aluminum alloy circumference area. Moreover, the Taguchi technique revealed minor corrosion in the aluminum samples dipped in a nitric acidic solution (HNO_3) for 216h. Analysis of variance (ANOVA) confirmed the contribution of two corrosion parameters to the corrosion rate of the aluminum alloy. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) revealed chloride traces over the surface of the highly corroded aluminum alloy.

Kamarska [48] carried out an electrochemical study using cyclic voltammetry, open circuit potential, and a digital microscope to compare the corrosion resistance of the 2011 aluminum alloy in three different acid solutions (H_2SO_4 , HCl , and HNO_3). The corrosion behavior of the alloy in the three acid solutions was determined using a potentiometric technique and its passivity over time was studied. The metal surface morphology was studied using a digital microscope. The obtained results indicate that the aluminum alloy 2011 corrodes to a greater extent in a hydrochloric acid solution than in a nitric and sulfuric acid solution. The results of the potentiometric tests show the formation of more stable passive films in the sulfuric acid solution than in the nitric and hydrochloric acid solution.

Hejazi et al. [49] contended that sodium benzoate is a salt of benzoic acid and is highly soluble in water, bland, and unscented. It is produced by mixing benzoic acid with sodium hydroxide. It does not exist organically; however, when combined with water, it creates benzoic acid, which exists natively in particular crops. Owing to its antifungal and antibacterial effects, it is used as a food preservative at tightly controlled dosages. Although some research show that it is effective in alleviating depression, pain, schizophrenia, autism spectrum disorders, and neurodegenerative illnesses, others claim that it is hazardous. It has been linked to mutagenesis, oxidative stress, hormone disruption, and decreased fertility. In recent years, concerns have been raised regarding its growing use as a preservative in meals, particularly processed foods. Owing to the large number of reports regarding its harmfulness as a food additive, researchers are increasingly looking for techniques to quantify the quantity of its molecules used in foods. High-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC-UV and LC-MS/MS) methods are two examples of instrumental analytical methods that have been developed and validated for quantifying components in foods and beverages. Several other approaches are also available for analyzing these materials. This study aimed to comprehensively discuss the safety profile of sodium benzoate and its potential usefulness, as well as the hazardous effects and methods of determining the quantity and identity of this component in food.

3.1.6 Research gaps in the corrosion inhibition of aluminum alloys in acidic environments

It is clear from the preceding review report that sodium benzoate is a non-toxic organic salt with significant industrial uses in acidic environments, including corrosion inhibition of aluminum alloys. Although it has excellent corrosion inhibitor properties, it works best to lower the corrosion rates of aluminum alloys in near-neutral to alkaline environments with pH values between 6 and 12. However, its inhibition performance data on aluminum alloys in highly acidic solutions of less than 5.5 pH has not been reconciled from the literature, and there is an indication that the corrosion inhibition decreases as the pH decreases downwards from 4. There are

also some recent claims that it converts to benzoic acid and possibly to benzene, a carcinogen. Therefore, further research with individual aluminum alloys and pH values in highly acidic conditions, using both electrochemical tests and field studies, is required to confirm some initial findings about its safety and optimal corrosion inhibition.

4.0 CONCLUSION

This study presents an up-to-date literature review report on sodium benzoate, showcasing it as an environmentally friendly organic salt that has significant applications in industries, cosmetics, medicines, foods, drinks, many personal body-care products, anticorrosive additives to paints or coatings, and corrosion inhibition in acidic environments. The review shows that sodium benzoate is manufactured on a large scale globally, with over 150,000 metric tons annually, and it is cheaply available in most countries, including Nigeria. It acts as a mixed-type non-toxic corrosion inhibitor of aluminum alloys in acidic media by forming protective, hydrophobic adsorbed films on them. It is particularly effective in reducing corrosion rates and maintaining the mechanical properties of aluminum alloys in acidic media, with an inhibition efficiency that increases with its increasing concentration and the alloy immersion time in the media. It is reportedly most effective in near-neutral to alkaline environments of 6-12 pH. Its inhibition performance data on aluminum alloys in highly acidic solutions of less than 5.5 pH has not been reconciled from literature, and there is an indication that its corrosion inhibition decreases as the pH decreases downwards from 4, with some claims that it converts to benzoic acid and benzene, a carcinogen. Therefore, sodium benzoate requires further research with individual aluminum alloy types and pH values in highly acidic conditions, including field studies apart from the conventional electrochemical corrosion tests, to confirm some initial findings about its safety and optimal corrosion inhibition for better usage.

REFERENCES

- TM Total Materia. Corrosion of Aluminum and Its Alloys: Forms of Corrosion, January 2008. Accessed January 15, 2026. <https://www.totalmateria.com/en-us/articles/corrosion-of-aluminum-forms-of-corrosion/>
- Alumeco Group. Corrosion of aluminum. Accessed January 15, 2026. <https://www.alumeco.at/aluminum/corrosion-of-aluminum/>
- M. Sangeetha, S. Rajendran, J. Sathiyabamaa, A. Krishnavenic, Inhibition of corrosion of aluminum and its alloys by extracts of green inhibitors. *Portugaliae Electrochimica Acta* 2013, 31(1), 41-52, DOI: 10.4152/pea.201301041
- Guma, T. N., & Aliyu, J. Effects of food chloride environment at a canteen on aluminum cookware corrosion, hardness integrity, and food safety. *Nigerian Journal of Engineering*, 28 (3), 50-55, 2021
- Guma, T. N. & Maikudi, M. M. Corrosion of aluminum metal in food environments and its associated health risk issues: A review. *Arid Zone Journal of Engineering, Technology and Environment*, 19(1), 71-84, 2023.
- Guma, T.N.& Durami, J.A. Assessment of alkaline food environment corrosion with some menus at a cadet mess on the tensile strength of aluminum 6063 alloy. *International Journal for Research in Applied Science & Engineering Technology*, 7(1), 621-630, 2019.
- Guma, T.N. & Sukuntuni, S.A. Effects of acidic food environment corrosion on impact strength of aluminum 6061 alloy: a case study with some menus at a Cadets' Mess. *International Journal of Engineering Trends and Technology*, 67(7), No. 3, 70-78, 2019.

- Guma, T.N. & Aliyu, M. Analysis of the inhibitory worth of noni (*morinda citrifolia*) fruit juice on corrosion of cookware aluminum by its chemical components. *Advanced International Journal of Material Science and Engineering*, 10(3), 8-25, 2025, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16536578>
- Guma, T.N., Adegor, K.A., Akindapo, J.O. & Akor, T. Inhibitory effects of calcium sulfate concentrations on cookware aluminum corrosion in highly acidic and alkaline media at elevated temperatures. *International Journal of Latest Technology in Engineering, Management and Applied Sciences*, 15(1), 2026, 139-166, <https://doi.org/10.51583/IJLTEMAS.2026.150100011>
- Nataraja Gummanar, Praveen Beekannahalli Mokshanatha, Pruthviraj Dyapur, & Ganesh Nituvall Yallappa. Organic corrosion inhibitors for aluminum-Based Alloys: A Review. *Letters in Applied NanoBioScience*, 124, 2023, 170, <https://doi.org/10.33263/LIANBS124.170>
- Okore, G. J., Okeke, P. I., Ehirim, A. I., Ejiogu, B. C., Okore, S., Amanze, K. O., & Nleonu, E. C. Green corrosion inhibition of aluminum in acidic environment using *Hibiscus sabdariffa* leaf extracts. *Preprints*, 2025, <https://doi.org/10.20944/preprints202502.1364.v1>
- Awad, Z. M., Abd, A. N., & Hassan, K. H. Corrosion prevention of aluminum in acidic media using *Cydonia vulgaris* leaf extract as an environmentally friendly corrosion inhibitor. *Journal of Biochemical Technology*, 9(3), 10-16, 2018.
- Răuță, D. I., Matei, E., & Avramescu, S. M. Recent development of corrosion inhibitors: types, mechanisms, electrochemical behavior, efficiency, and environmental impact. *Technologies*, 13(3), 103, 2025. <https://doi.org/10.3390/technologies13030103>
- Abd El Haleem, S. M., Abd El Wanees, S., Abd El Aal, E. E., & Farouk, A. Factors affecting the corrosion behavior of aluminum in acid solutions. I. Nitrogen and/or sulfur-containing organic compounds as corrosion inhibitors for Al in HCl solutions. *Corrosion Science*, Vol. 68, 1-13, 2013, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.corsci.2012.03.021>.
- Fayomi, O. S. I., Anawe, P. A. L., & Daniyan, A. (2018). The impact of drugs as corrosion inhibitors on aluminum alloy in coastal-acidified medium. In *Corrosion Inhibitors, Principles and Recent Applications*. InTec, <https://doi.org/10.5772/intechopen.72942>
- Raviprabha K, Bhat RS, Bhat SI, Nagaraj P, Jyothi K. Corrosion inhibition study of 6061 aluminum alloy in the presence of ethyl 5-methyl-1-(4-nitrophenyl)-1H-1,2,3-triazole-4-carboxylate (NTE) in hydrochloric acid. *Helion*, 9(5), 2023, e16036.
- Prathap Singh, S., Gerald, M., Arul Selvan, P., Jose Aloysius, P., Ravichandran, K., & Vinoth B. Effect of acidic solution and immersion duration on the corrosion behavior of the aluminum 6061 alloy, *Materials Today: Proceedings*, 2023, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.matpr.2023.08.232>.
- Nwosu, F. O., Owate, I. O., & Osarolube, E. Acidic corrosion inhibition mechanism of aluminum alloy using green inhibitors. *American Journal of Materials Science*, 8(3), 2018, 45-50, Doi: 10.5923/j.materials.20180803.01

- Guma, T. N., Madakson, P. B., Yawas, D. S., & Aku, S. Y. Sodium benzoate and bitumen coatings as inhibitors of corrosion degradation of mechanical properties of low carbon steel, *Journal of Chemical Mechanical and Engineering Practice, International Perspective* 2, 34-44, 2012,
- Shubham Pharmachem Pvt. Ltd. Sodium Benzoate – Promising Application in Medicine, 09 March, 2025, Accessed, 23 February, 2026, at <https://www.shubham.co.in/sodium-benzoate-promising-application-in-medicine/>
- Lakshmi, K.G., Vytheeswari, K., 2024. A review on: analysis of sodium benzoate preserve and impacts on Health. *International Journal of Novel Research and Development*, 9(3), 2024, c84-c87.
- Lennerz BS, Vafai SB, Delaney NF, Clish CB, Deik AA, Pierce KA, Ludwig DS, Mootha VK. Effects of sodium benzoate, a widely used food preservative, on glucose homeostasis and metabolic profiles in humans. *Mol Genet Metab.* 2015 Jan;114(1):73-9. Doi: 10.1016/j.ymgme.2014.11.010. Epub 2014 Nov 15. PMID: 25497115; PMCID: PMC4289147.
- Nimbasia Stabilizer, 16 July 2024. What is sodium benzoate? Its benefits, side effects, and uses? Accessed 12 February 2026, at <https://www.nimbasia.com/blogs/what-is-sodium-benzoate-its-benefits-side-effects-and-uses.html>
- Ataman Chemicals. Accessed February 12, 2026, at <https://atamankimya.com/sayfalaralfabe.asp?LanguageID=2&cid=3&id=2872&id2=5679>
- Healthline. What is sodium benzoate? Everything you need to know. Accessed February 10, 2026, at <https://www.healthline.com/nutrition/sodium-benzoate#safety>
- Fortune Business Insights. Chemicals and Materials/Sodium Benzoate Market. Accessed February 12, 2026, at <https://www.fortunebusinessinsights.com/sodium-benzoate-market-111441>
- NPCS. Manufacturing business of benzoic acid/sodium benzoate. Accessed February 15, 2026, at <https://www.niir.org/profile-project-reports/profile/5260/manufacturing-business-benzoic-acid-sodium-benzoate.html>
- Walczak-Nowicka Ł J, Herbet M. Sodium benzoate-harmfulness and potential use in therapies for disorders related to the nervous system: a review. *Nutrients.* 2022;14(7):1497, Doi: 10.3390/nu14071497. PMID: 35406109; PMCID: PMC9003278
- Mohammed, DH, Issa, HM. Mini-Review on Sodium Benzoate: Its Uses, Adverse Effects, and Environmental Impact as a Pharmaceutical Product. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/395669229>. Accessed Feb 23, 2026.
- Pongsetkul, J., & Benjakul, S. The use of sodium benzoate on shelf-life and quality attributes of dried chili fish paste stored in different packaging containers. *Foods*, 10(8), 2021, 1802, <https://doi.org/10.3390/foods10081802>

- Kaur A, Gill PPS, & Jawandha SK. Effect of sodium benzoate application on quality and enzymatic changes of pear fruits during low temperature. *J Food Sci Technol.*56(7), 2019, 3391-3398, Doi: 10.1007/s13197-019-03823-5. Epub 2019 Jun 10. PMID: 31274907; PMCID: PMC6582190.
- Shahmohammadi, M., Javadi, M. & Nassiri-Asl, M. An overview on the effects of sodium benzoate as a preservative in food products. *Biotechnology and Health Sciences*, 3(3), 2016, <https://doi.org/10.17795/bhs-35084><https://doi.org/10.17795/bhs-35084>
- Linke, B. G. O., Casagrande, T. A. C., & Cardoso, L. A. C. (2018). Food additives and their health effects: A review on preservative sodium benzoate. *African Journal of Biotechnology*, 17(10), 306-310.
- Azuma, S.L., Quartey, N.K-A. & Oforu, I.W, Sodium benzoate in non-alcoholic carbonated (soft) drinks: Exposure and health risks, *Sci. Afr.* 10, 2020, e00611, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sciaf.2020.e00611>.
- Nik, W.S., Oladokun, O.S., Goh, E.G. & Rosliza, R.. Evaluation of inhibitory action of sodium benzoate on corrosion behavior of AA6063 in seawater. *International Journal of Technology* 1(1):20-28, 2010, DOI: 10.14716/ijtech.v1i1.997
- Abdul Hady bin Abu Bakar. Sodium Benzoate as aluminum Corrosion Inhibitor in Acidic Media. A Research Project Report submitted in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the Degree of Bachelor of Science (Hons.) Applied Chemistry, Universiti Teknologi MARA, Faculty of Applied Sciences, November, 2008.
- Rafi-ud-din, Shafqat, Q. A., Shahzad, M., Ahmad, E., Asghar, Z., Rafiq, N., Qureshi, A. H., Syed, W. A. & Pasha, R. A. Inhibitor effects of sodium benzoate on corrosion resistance of Al6061-B4C composites in NaCl and H3BO3 solutions. *Journal of Materials Research, Express*, IOP Publishing, 3(12), 2016, 126501, <https://doi.org/10.1088/2053-1513/12/12/126501>
- Wormwell, F., Mercer, A.D. & Ison, H.C.K. Sodium benzoate and sodium nitrite as corrosion-inhibitors in ethylene glycol anti-freeze solutions. II. Investigations in working vehicles, *Journal of Applied Chemistry*, 3(3), 2007, 133-144, DOI: 10.1002/jctb.5010030309
- Pruthviraj R.D. Corrosion studies of AA2024 in sea water using sodium benzoate as an Inhibitor, *J. Mater. Sci. Eng.*, 5(2), 226, 2016, Doi:10.4172/2169-0022.1000226
- Wong, L. S., Wong, S. D., Liang, W., Chin, C., & Sim, S. F. Assessment of the potential of sodium benzoate as anti-microbial and anti-corrosion agent in coolant. *Science and Technology Asia*, 30(4),2025, 68–81. <https://ph02.tci-thaijo.org/index.php/SciTechAsia/article/view/258090>
- Parveen, M., Mobin, M., Zehra, S. *et al.* L-proline mixed with sodium benzoate as sustainable inhibitor for mild steel corrosion in 1M HCl: An experimental and theoretical approach. *Sci. Rep.* 8, 7489 (2018). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-018-24143-2>
- Muzathik, A.M, Ahmad, M.F. Kamales, B. Nik, & Wan, W.B. International Conference. 20-22 October, 2012. Kuala Terengganu, Malaysia, 2012, 1-6. <http://ir.lib.seu.ac.lk/handle/123456789/2541>

- Uwiringiyimana, E., Oâ€™, D.P. S, Ifeoma V. J., & Feyisayo V. A. The effect of corrosion inhibitors on stainless steels and aluminum alloys: A review, 10(2), No, 451AB3257933, pp. 23-32, 2016, <https://doi.org/10.5897/AJPAC2016.0676>
- R. Rosliza, W.B. Wan Nik, HB. Senin The effect of inhibitor on the corrosion of aluminum alloys in acidic solutions, *Materials Chemistry and Physics*, 107(2/3), 2008, 281-288
- Rosliza, R., Seoh, S. Y., wan sani wan nik, S., Senin, H. B. Corrosion behavior of aluminum alloys in acidic media. *AIP Conf. Proceedings*. 909, 220–222, 2007, <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.2739855>
- Prabhu Deepa, Rao Padmalatha Corrosion behavior of 6063 aluminum alloy in acidic and in alkaline media. *Arabian Journal of Chemistry*, 10 (2_suppl), 2017; S2234-S2244, Doi: 10.1016/j.arabjc.2013.07.05910.1016/j.arabjc.2013.07.059
- S. Prathap Singh, M. Gerald Arul Selvan, P. Jose Aloysius, P. Ravichandran, K. Vinoth Babu, Effect of acidic solution and immersion duration on the corrosion behavior of the aluminum 6061 alloy, *Materials Today: Proceedings*, 2023, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.matpr.2023.08.232>.
- Kamarska, K. Comparative study on the corrosion behavior of aluminum alloy 2011 in different acidic media. *AIP Conf. Proc.* 2980, 060014, 2024, <https://doi.org/10.1063/5.0185433>
- Hejazi, L., Mahboubi-Rabbani, M., Mahdavi, V., Alemi, M., Khanniri, E., & Bayanati, M. (2024). A critical review on sodium benzoate from health effects to analytical methods. *Results in Chemistry*, Vol. 11, 2024, 101798, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rechem.2024.101798>.